

Family life with digital platforms

How are digital platforms embedded in the lives and practices of modern families?

My wife got lost while driving a few times. But if I can check this app, I know where she is. I can tell her where she needs to go.

Bertil (78), grandfather, Norway

What place do digital platforms hold in families, and what do they mean for relationships between generations?

Background and context

Digital platforms such as social media, messaging services, and apps that help us organize family life have taken on an increasingly central role in our daily routines. Digital platforms are mediators of online content, with design and user interfaces that enable interaction between algorithms, data, and content created by users. Research examining how families' daily lives and relationships have changed due to the use of platforms and their algorithms is lacking. PlatFAMs studied how the immersiveness of digital platforms has contributed to changing our family lives – for children, parents, and grandparents. The study was conducted in Norway, UK, Estonia, Poland, Romania, and Spain.

Objectives and methodology

The PlatFAMs project aimed to understand first, how family generations *navigate* and experience the platformisation of family life, second, the *negotiations* and consequences for relationships between generations with their use of platforms, and third, how they understand the *platformed future* for families. We collected 313 stories about everyday life with digital platforms from 103 three-generation families (children, parents, and grandparents) across six European countries. Ten families were followed up to dig deeper into generational differences, and to collaborate on designing their own 'Perfect Family App'. In addition, we used a European quantitative dataset with information about children and their parents (EU Kids Online 2018).

The PlatFAMs full sample

313 participants
from 104 families

Key findings and impact

As more aspects of family life move onto platforms and are shaped by algorithms, family members' different roles and responsibilities shift.

We found that families view digital platforms as a future infrastructure for communication and care, while still believing that face-to-face interaction is irreplaceable. Many describe a sense of powerlessness toward Big Tech companies, along with concerns about privacy, data storage and algorithms. Clear generational patterns emerged: grandparents are 'partially platformised', parents form a 'transitional generation' that sets the platform rules in the family, and children and adolescents represent the 'future platformised generation' – active but bound by family norms.

Ambivalence is pervasive: platforms bring the family together but also segment members into different 'realities'. They enable care across long distances, while attention and face-to-face interaction without platforms remain most important for those living together. Streaming platforms are part of many families' routines – for example, weekend TV evenings – and help strengthen family bonds.

At the same time, platforms rely on individualised interfaces and profiles that may undermine a shared 'family time'. Mutual tracking and monitoring among family members is largely normalised and described as care and safety, rooted in mistrust of the outside world or in mutual relational trust and openness. Local parenting norms shape platform use differently across countries.

The project has brought nuanced understanding of key aspects of how platforms influence families; through surveillance, intimacy, care and relational agency. Results increase NGOs' development of strategies towards better understanding of how generations deal with and use the affordances of platforms and apps. The social impact on social institutions other than the family will also be apparent, such as education, health. Recognising these patterns will help families and policymakers support safer, more inclusive and balanced practices.

PlatFAMs has resulted in a book on the platformisation of the family, a family game designed to stimulate discussion about dilemmas and paradoxes inherent in their digital everyday lives, and numerous scientific articles in leading journals. Project website: <https://digitalfamilies.eu/>

Instead of us using technology less, I think when more things are invented – more cool and useful things – it will make us more addicted instead of making us less addicted to screens. Because technology gives you cool things, but also bad ones.

Aura (9), daughter, Spain

PlatFAMs Card Game:
 A conversation-driven card game developed for intergenerational dialogue and reflection on family-related ethical dilemmas.

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